

Assessment of Pesticide Residues in Papaya Fruit and Its Impact on Consumer Health

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ABSTRACT

Detection pesticide residues is an important tool to ensure food safety and protect consumers from potential toxic effects. This study was conducted to determine the levels of several pesticide residues in papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) fruits using LC–MS/MS analysis. A total of six pesticide residues Acetamiprid (R), Carbendazim, Emamectin benzoate, Imidacloprid, Metalaxyl and Profenofos were detected in the analyzed samples. From these, Profenofos (2.689 mg/kg) and Emamectin benzoate (0.216 mg/kg) were found to exceed their respective maximum residue limits (MRLs) by 0.01 mg/kg and 0.02 mg/kg, indicating significant non-compliance with food safety standards. The high concentrations of profenofos, a neurotoxic organophosphate compound, are of particular concern due to its potential endocrine-disrupting and neurotoxic effects. The presence of multiple residues, including four pesticides, at permissible limits, indicates a pattern of widespread pesticide use during the pre-harvest phase and possible misuse or overuse of agrochemicals, which is likely related to poor adherence to Good Agricultural Practices (GAP). These findings highlight the urgent need for regular residue monitoring, strict regulatory controls, and training of farmers on safe pesticide use. Furthermore, the promotion of organic and integrated pest management (IPM) strategies is strongly recommended to ensure the safety and sustainability of fresh produce and to comply with international food safety standards.

Keywords: Papaya, MRL, Pesticide residues, Fruit, Consumer health.

INTRODUCTION

The agriculture field is changes forcefully due to the high demand for food as the population increases. Pesticides are those substances that kill pests that eat fruits and vegetables and decrease productivity. To increases quality and quantity fruits and vegetables, they must be provided with proper fertilizers and sprayed with pesticides. There are various pesticides such as insecticides, herbicides, fungicides, and bactericides. Pesticides are classified into organic and inorganic; organic pesticides are chemical-free, including organochlorines, organophosphates, carbamates, and pyrethroids. Inorganic pesticides contain which contain copper, sulphur, ferrous sulfate, and copper sulfate. Sulfur was the first pesticide known to humans (Kaur, et al., 2019). The nature-based pesticides such as pyrethrum, derived from chrysanthemums, and rotenone, derived from the roots of tropical vegetables, were developed in the

19th century. In 2020 the study says that the number of pesticides consumed by the world would be around 3.5 million tonnes (Savant, et al., 2010). As per the available data, 61702 mega-tonnes of pesticides have been used in 2019–2020 in India, and Maharashtra is the leading state with 13243 mega-tonnes of pesticides used (Government of India, 2023). As of the year 2021, there are a total of 299 pesticides that are registered in India. As per the Indian pesticide market value in the year 2020 was INR 232 billion. Farmers can spray the pesticides to achieve high agricultural yield. But on the other side, the high toxic chemical substances will be used in pesticides was very harmful and dangerous to human health (Government of India, 2023). The person who spraying the pesticide can inhale these pesticides indirectly, causing respiratory problems. If pesticide particles come in contact with the eyes, the person loses vision with irritation of the eyes to a certain extent. Pesticides are used in modern agriculture to

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increase the agricultural yield. Currently, India is the largest producer of fruits and the second largest producer of vegetables after China (FAO, 2017). Pesticides including organochlorines, organophosphorus, carbamate, phthalimide, and pyrethroid was used to prevent pest attack and diseases in fruits and vegetables in India (Zhang, et al., 2011). India is the largest agricultural pesticide consumers worldwide and is the second largest producer of pesticides in Asia (Mostafalou and Abdollahi, 2013). It is reported that recent modifications and validation of QuEChERS-dSPE technique coupled to LC-MS and GC-MS system for the determination of pesticide and agrochemical residues in fruits and vegetables. The modification of QuEChERS-dSPE techniques in provides excellent validation parameters such as range of relative recoveries, quantitation and detection limits of pesticides determined in various samples of fruits and vegetables (AOAC, 2008; Lawal, et al., 2018). screen the pesticide residues in summer fruits and vegetables from Kanpur, India. They can study 12 commonly used pesticides on 23 commonly consumed vegetables and 12 fruits by using gas chromatography. They can find organophosphate and organochloride pesticides on fruit and vegetables samples but malathion organophosphate pesticides found maximum amount on both fruit and vegetables sample (Sarma, et al., 2019).

The presence of pesticide residues in fruits poses a significant public health risk. Carbamates, organophosphates, pyrethroids and neonicotinoids are commonly used in fruit cultivation and have been linked to a wide range of acute and chronic toxicities. Long-term exposure, even at low levels, can cause developmental defects, endocrine disruption, neurotoxicity, carcinogenic effects, and reproductive disorders. Children are particularly susceptible due to their high intake relative to body weight and immature detoxification systems (Sanghi and Tewari, 2001). In addition to human health, overuse of pesticides contributes to ecological imbalances. Persistent pesticide residues disrupt microbial diversity in soil, pollute water bodies through runoff, and harm non-target organisms such as pollinators, natural predators, and aquatic animals. Furthermore, indiscriminate use of pesticides promotes the development of insect resistance, leading to the need

for higher doses or more toxic alternatives creating a vicious cycle of chemical dependency (Aktar, et al., 2009). Pesticides protect about a third of all agricultural products worldwide, yet their widespread use has negative impacts on ecosystems (Qu, C., et al., 2019). Poor management/mismanagement or lack of knowledge (misuse and overuse) can result in pesticides accumulating and causing more damage than on crops. Label instructions for use and safety recommendations such as wearing rubber gloves and goggles to protect against exposure are not effectively followed by users (a common cause of pesticide incidents, EPA) (Sanborn, et al., 2004).

The increasing demand for food worldwide, especially in densely populated areas like India, has led to an increase in the use of pesticides in agriculture. Although essential for pest control, overuse of pesticides can seriously threaten public health and food safety. Various agrochemicals are frequently used for pest control on the commercially important and nutritionally dense papaya (*Carica papaya*), resulting in residues exceeding the maximum residue limit (MRL). The objective of this study was to identify pesticide residues in papaya fruits collected from Nanded, a local market in India, and to assess any potential health risks associated with their consumption.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sampling

A total of 25 fruit samples were collected in Nanded district between January 2022 and January 2025. These samples were collected from various locations such as small farms, restaurants, community markets, homes and street vendors. For collection, a total of approximately 1 kg was randomly selected from various locations from a single source, packed and labeled. The collected samples were then transported to the laboratory and kept in cold storage until required for processing. Prior to analysis, the collected fruits were pooled and homogenized. A 15 g portion of this homogenized sample was taken for immediate analysis or stored at 4°C for analysis within 24 hours.

2.2 Pesticide Residue Analysis by QuEChERS Method

This method is used for analysis of pesticide residues in Fruits like Grapes, Pomegranate, Mango and Okra etc. in the range of 0.01mg/kg to 10mg/kg except fipronil 0.005 mg/kg. The sample containing residues more than 0.2mg/kg residue will be diluted to bring the response within the working range and analyzed again (AOAC, 2007).

Pesticide residues are extracted from fresh fruits samples by using ethyl acetate based extraction method. The cleaned ethyl acetate extract is analyzed by gas chromatograph tandem Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS) using full scan or MS/MS mode for the GC amenable compounds with Electron Impact ionization source. The ethyl acetate extract after evaporation and reconstitution in methanol with acidified water analyzed by high performance liquid chromatography tandem Mass Spectrometer (LC-MS/MS) with electro-spray ionization by using Multi-Reaction Monitoring mode for the LC amenable compounds. Qualitative and quantitative analysis is done by external standard calibration method (Oulkar, et al 2011).

2.3 Chemicals Equipment and Instruments

2.3.1 Equipment's: Blender, Homogenizer, Centrifuge, GCMS-MS Triple Quadrupole, LCMS-MS Triple Quadrupole, Balance, Centrifuge Tube (FEP) 50 ml, Micro centrifuge tube- 2 ml, Micropipette- 1 ml, Vials -2 ml and Volumetric Pipette- 10 ml.

2.3.2 Reagents: Methanol (LCMS grade), Ethyl Acetate (Dried), Water (HPLC Grade), Anhydrous Sodium Sulphate (pre-heated for 3 hrs. at 5000C), Acetic Acid Glacial (HPLC Grade), Primary Secondary Amine (PSA), Formic Acid, Ammonium Formate and Anhydrous Sodium Acetate.

2.3.3 Standard Preparation:

Stock solutions of individual pesticide standards were prepared by accurately weighing 10 (0.1) mg of each analyte in a volumetric flask (certified A class) and dissolving 10 (0.1) g in ethyl acetate. These were stored in dark vials at 4 °C. A working standard mixture of 1 mg L⁻¹ was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution, from which calibration

standards (5-250 ng mL⁻¹) were prepared by serial dilution with ethyl acetate (Pujeri, et al., 2015).

2.3.4 Preparation of Linear dilutions: Pipette out required volume from 6.1 to 10ml volumetric flasks for the different levels (5, 10, 25, 50, 100, 200 ppb) of dilutions and make up to the mark with appropriate solvent. Calculations were done by formula $C_1V_1=C_2V_2$.

2.3.5 Reagent Preparation:

- i. 10% diethylene glycol solution in methanol- Dissolve 10 mL of diethylene glycol in methanol to make the final volume to 100 mL.
- ii. 0.1% acetic acid solution in water- Dissolve 0.1 mL of acetic acid in methanol to make the final volume to 100 mL.
- iii. Phase A: 5mM ammonium formate in methanol & water (20:80): Add 0.317 g ammonium formate to 1000 mL graduated cylinder. Dilute to 1000 mL with 800 mL HPLC water and 200 mL methanol. Filter through 0.2 μ Nylon 6,6 membrane filter using solvent filtration assembly. Sonicate for 5 min for degassing the phase.
- iv. Phase B: 5mM ammonium formate in methanol & water (90:10): Add 0.317 g ammonium formate to 1000 mL graduated cylinder. Dilute to 1000 mL with 100 mL HPLC water and 900 mL methanol. Filter through 0.2 μ Nylon 6,6 membrane filter using solvent filtration assembly. Sonicate for 5 min for degassing the phase.

2.4. Sample Preparation Procedure

2.4.1 Homogenization: Crush 2.0 kg. of the papaya fruits sample and homogenize the whole sample.

Procedure

2.4.2 Extraction: Transfer 10 gm (± 0.1g) of the homogenized sample in 50 ml centrifuge tube, add 10mL of HPLC grade water. Add 10 ml of Ethyl Acetate. Add 1.5gm anhydrous Sodium Acetate and 10 gm anhydrous Sodium Sulphate. Homogenize and Centrifuge 4000 rpm for 5 min.

2.4.3 Clean-up for LCMS-MS: Take 5 ml of the supernatant from 7.2.4 in a test tube containing 50mg of PSA. Vortex and centrifuge to settle the PSA, Pipette out 2mL of the supernatant, add 0.2mL of 10% DEG (in Methanol) and evaporate to dryness under Nitrogen. Dissolve residue in 1.5 ml Methanol, add 0.5 mL of 1% Acetic acid and transfer to 2 ml micro centrifuge tube vortex for 30sec. Centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 5 minute. Take out the supernatant and filter through 0.22 μ membrane filter. Inject 5 μ L into LC MS-MS.

2.4.4 Clean-up for GCMS-MS: Take 1 ml of the supernatant from 7.2.4 in 2ml Micro centrifuge tube, which contains 25mg of PSA, shakes vigorously for 30s on vortex. Centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 1 min (Mathur and Tannan, 1998; Subash, et al., 2018).

2.4.5 Sequence of Injections: a. Inject solvent blank, b. Inject matrix blank, c. Inject standards of suitable concentration within calibration range, d. Inject samples, e. After every six samples inject standard of suitable concentration within range.

2.5. Analysis by QuEChERS Method

2.5.1 Analysis by LC-MS/MS: Instrument conditions,

- i. Column: C-18 50mm X 4.6mm Particle size 2.7 μ .
- ii. Mobile Phase: A. 5mM Ammonium Formate in 0.1% FA in Water.

B. 5mM Ammonium Formate in 0.1% FA in Methanol

- iii. Flow rate: 0.8 ml/min
- iv. Source: \pm ESI
- v. Column Temp: 450C
- vi. Injection Volume: 5 μ L
- vii. LC Gradients:

2.5.2 Analysis by GCMS-MS: GC Conditions:

- i. Column: Stationary Phase: 5% Phenyl Dimethyl Polysiloxane-MS Suitable, 325 °C, 30m x 250 μ m x 0.25 μ m.
- ii. Oven Temperature: 70°C-1.0min-20°C/min.-150°C-1.0min-3°C/min-200°C-0.0min-8°C/min-285°C- 4min. Total Run Time – 37.29min
- iii. Inlet: 250°C
- iv. Detector Source: EI Positive
- v. Carrier flow: He: 1.2ml/min.
- vi. Auxiliary Temp.: 285°C

2.6 Calculation:

$$\text{Residue } \mu\text{g/gm} = \frac{\text{Area of sample}}{\text{Area of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Conc. of standard in } \mu\text{g/ml}}{\text{Weight. Of sample in gm}} \times \text{X Dilution factor}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Screening of Papaya for Multipesticide Contaminations

The LC-MS/MS analysis of papaya samples showed the presence of six different pesticide residues, two of which were found above the MRL (Maximum Residue Limit), indicating significant violations of food safety standards. The pesticides detected included Acetamiprid (R), Carbendazim, Emamectin benzoate, Imidacloprid, Metalyxil and Profenophos. Of these, Profenophos showed the highest concentration of 2.689 mg/kg, which was far higher than its MRL of 0.01 mg/kg. This is particularly worrisome because Profenophos is an organophosphate known for its neurotoxic and hormonal disruption effects. It is followed by Emamectin benzoate was found above their respective MRLs, 0.216 mg/kg (MRL: 0.02 mg/kg). This also indicated excessive use during the pre-harvest stage.

Acetamiprid (R), Carbendazim, Imidacloprid and Metalyxil these four pesticides were within the permissible limits, although their presence indicates the use of various chemical pesticides. The finding of multiple residues analysis, some pesticides residues

showed above the MRL and some showed below, it indicates the possibility of excessive or misuse of agro-chemicals in papaya fruits, perhaps without following GAP (Good Agricultural Practices). Our findings highlighted the need for strict regulatory

monitoring, farmer education on the use of safe pesticide, and implementation of biological pest management strategies to ensure the safety of fresh produce.

Table 1. Quantitative Assessment of Pesticide Residues above MRL in Papaya by LC-MS/MS

Sr. No.	Name of Pesticides	Result in (ml/kg)	Harmonized EU-MRL (ml/kg)	LOQ (ml/kg)	Above MRL
1	Acetamiprid (R)	0.01	0.02	0.01	NO
2	Carbendazim	0.523	2	0.01	NO
3	Imidacloprid	0.015	0.50	0.01	NO
4	Emamectin benzoate	0.216	0.02	0.01	YES
5	Metalyxil	0.039	0.05	0.01	NO
6	Profenophos	2.689	0.01	0.01	YES

Note: BLQ: Bellow the Level of Quantification, LOQ: Limit of Quantification, NA: MRLs Not Available

Figure 1: Quantitative Assessment of Pesticide Residues above MRL in Papaya by LC-MS/MS

Figure 2: Chromatogram of Pesticide Residues above MRL in Papaya by LC-MS/MS

Table 2: Quantitation Results

Compound	RT	Response	Final Conc	Units
Carbendazim	4.989	75236973	523.5999	ng/ml
Imidacloprid	6.109	208350	15.5585	ng/ml
Acetamiprid	7.138	17807	9.7924	ng/ml
Metalaxyl	12.358	13990103	39.8641	ng/ml
Profenophos	15.967	47707682	2689.3137	ng/ml
Emamactin benzoate	16.050	1504761	216.5115	ng/ml

Figure 3: Graphical representation of 06 Pesticide Residues above MRL in Papaya by LC-MS/MS

Similar trends were also reported by Gormez, et al. (2023), indicating the consistent presence of these residues in mandarin produce. In the study they observed that the concentrations of pesticides also varied significantly, ranging from 0.026 to 39.386 mg kg for phosphonic acid and 0.010 to 1.485 mg kg for spirotetramat. The study is consistent with the findings by the Jallow, et al. (2017), found that residues of several commonly used pesticides in the 150 fruit and vegetable samples tested, 21% exceeded the MRL, indicating potential health risks despite 79% being within acceptable limits. Sixteen of the 34 pesticides tested were found to be present, with several - such as imidacloprid, deltamethrin, cypermethrin, malathion, acetamiprid,

monocrotophos, chlorpyrifos-methyl and diazinon - exceeding their respective MRLs. These health risks are worsened by cumulative exposure to multiple residues and are particularly significant in vulnerable groups, including children and pregnant women (Sawyer, et al., 2024). The widespread use of pesticides like Glyphosate, Chlorpyrifos, and Neonicotinoids in farming has been directly connected to a range of adverse health effects in humans, from immediate symptoms such as headaches and nausea to more serious consequences affecting neurological and reproductive systems (Ahmad, et al., 2024; Cimino, et al., 2017). Long-term or repeated exposure to certain pesticides may also cause chronic illnesses, including cancer, fertility

problems, and neurodegenerative diseases (Shekhar, et al., 2024). The levels of pesticide residues found in food after harvest are beyond consumers' control and pose significant health threats (Mahmoudi, et al., 2022). Additionally, during food processing, pesticides can break down into more harmful metabolic products, increasing their toxicity and significantly changing the food's final composition, which can lead to health issues (Bajwa and Sandhu, 2014). Moreover, health impacts depend on factors such as the chemical properties of the pesticide, the dose and route of exposure, and individual susceptibility (Daniel et al., 2024). Still, the buildup of residues from eating contaminated produce is directly associated with chronic health problems like cancer, reproductive issues, and endocrine disruption (Urvashi, et al., 2024). The possibility of long-term health impacts, which might appear years after even minimal exposure through contaminated food and water, emphasizes the need for strict monitoring and regulation of pesticide residues (Munoz-Bautisat, 2025).

CONCLUSION

LC-MS/MS analysis of papaya samples clearly shows the occurrence of multiple pesticide residues, which led to serious lapses in compliance with established food safety standards. Of the six compounds detected Acetamiprid (R), Carbendazim, Emamectin benzoate, Imidacloprid, metalaxyl and Profenofos the two pesticides such as Profenofos (2.689 mg/kg; MRL 0.01 mg/kg) and Emamectin benzoate (0.216 mg/kg; MRL 0.02 mg/kg), exceeded their maximum residue limits (MRL) respectively. The elevated levels of neurotoxic organophosphates known for their endocrine-disrupting properties indicate serious toxicological and regulatory concerns.

Although Acetamiprid (R), Carbendazim, Imidacloprid and Metalaxyl were found within permissible limits, their co-occurrence reflects a pattern of widespread pesticide use, likely resulting from indiscriminate use and non-compliance with Good Agricultural Practices (GAP). This contamination profile highlights the risk of long-term dietary exposure and the urgent need for strict residue monitoring and enforcement of pesticide regulations.

To mitigate these risks, it is necessary to strengthen regulatory oversight, increase farmer awareness and training on safe pesticide use, and integrate organic and environmentally sound pest management strategies. Such measures are essential not only to protect consumer health, but also to ensure the sustainability, export viability and international food safety compliance of papaya and other tropical fruit production systems.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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